

IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF SALINITY ON SOIL PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract

Salinity and sodicity are major soil problems leading to the deterioration of soil fertility. The current study was carried out at District Swabi for the assessment of the impacts of salinity on soil physico-chemical properties. Soil samples were collected from both saline and non saline areas and were analyzed for physical and chemical properties. Study findings showed that the physio chemical properties of saline were much different from that of the non saline lands. The texture of saline land was found to be silt loam while that of non saline was sandy loam. The average pH, EC, soil bulk density, SAR (Sodium adsorption Ratio), Soil Extractable Sodium (Na^+), soil Extractable K^+ , of saline lands were found to be higher as compared to the non saline soil while soil porosity, Phosphorous (P), NO_3^- , $\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+}$, of non saline soil was greater as compared to the saline soils. Study findings showed that salinity has great effects on the physical and chemical properties of the soil because it causes to reduce the amount of some micro and macro nutrients and increases the amount of salts like Na^+ , K^+ , which leads to the higher SAR (sodium absorption ratio). To facilitate future measurement of soil salinity and sodicity improvements in study area and permit adoption of appropriate salinity management practices this study suggests management practices like using planting of salt-tolerant crops, agro forestry, applications of lime (gypsum or oyster shells), organic manures and residues, leaching and drainage.

INTRODUCTION

Salinity is a major factor in reducing the soil composition and thus the crops growth and productivity throughout the world. Salinity is wide spread problem which has affected 7% of the total continental extent while 77% of the land has been salinized by human (Ghassemi *et al.*, 1995). Approximately 25-30% of irrigated lands in the United States have crop yields that are negatively affected due to soil salinity (Ghassemi *et al.* 1995). Studies suggest that around \$11 billion annually crops production loss occur due to salinity worldwide (Ghassemi *et al.* 1995).

It has been estimated so far that about 23% of the cultivated lands are saline while about 37% are sodic. The recent numeral for the amount of salt affected soils in Pakistan is 61, 73,000 hectares (Anon., 1999). It includes both inland and coastal areas most of which are saline and are not suitable for cultivation of most of the crops. The surface salinity of Pakistan is 72% in which 84% exist in Punjab, 78% in Khyberpukhtonkhwa, 50% in Sindh and 74% in Baluchistan while profile salinity of Pakistan is 6% reported by SCARP in which 6% is from the soil of Punjab and Khyber Pukhtonkhwa, Sindh and Baluchistan soils are having 50% profile soil salinity (Ghias, 2008).

Generally all soils contain some soluble salts, but when soil and environmental conditions allow the concentration in soil layers to rise above a level which causes to affect the agricultural production, environmental health, and economic welfare, then

soil salinity becomes an issue of land degradation. Soil salinity refers to the state of building up of the soluble salts in the soil dominated by sodium chloride which is measured in decimenes per meter (ds/m) or in parts per million (Khaier, 2003). Salinity of soil is not only associated with sodium chloride but it may be the combination of sodium, calcium, potassium, magnesium, chlorides, nitrates, sulfates, bicarbonates and carbonates. Salinity includes the types of Na salinity, Ca & Mg salinity and saline sodicity (Gehad, 2003). In agriculture perspective saline soils are those which contain enough neutral soluble salts in the root zone which negatively affect the growth of most crops. Salinity is categorized into two type's natural salinization or primary salinization results from the accumulation of salts over long periods of time, through natural processes (Isbell *et al.*, 1983), while Secondary or induced salinity results from human activities (Szabolcs, 1989; Minhas and Sharma, 2003).

Impacts of Salinity and Sodicity on Soil

Soil salinity is the buildup of salts to such a point that it ruins the soil and vegetation. Salt buildup can result in three types of soils: saline, saline-sodic and sodic (Abrol and Yadav, 1988; Szabolcs, 1989). Salt affected soils are categorized on the basis of ESP (Exchangeable Sodium Percentage) or SAR (Sodium Adsorption Ratio) and EC.

Classification criteria of salt affected soils.

Nature of soil	EC (dsm ⁻¹)	ESP	SAR
Saline	≥4	<15	<15
Sodic	<4	≥15	≥15
Saline Sodic	≥4	≥15	≥15
Normal Soil	<4	<15	<15

Source: Bohn *et al.*, (1985).

Salinity has the opposite effect on the physical structure of soil as it causes to bind and aggregation of soil the fine particles and leads to flocculation. When the amount of salts in soil is high it will

promotes the aggregation of soil particles (Hanson *et al.*, 1999). When the salinity value exceeds from about 960 mg/L (1.5 dS/m) the flocculation process is accelerated and it is also enhanced when the salinity of irrigation water becomes greater than 0.5

dS/m (Hanson *et al.*, 1999). The high salt concentration in soil causes to push the adsorbed cations closer to soil particles and thus keeping the soil aggregates together (Miller and Donahue, 1995). Sodium has also adversely effects on soil physical structure. The primary effect of high sodium concentrations is the soil dispersion and clay platelet and aggregate swelling. When the amount of sodium ions in the soil increases the binding forces between the clay particles are disrupted and thus the soil particle separates from each other and is dispersed (Miller and Donahue, 1999; Ayers and Westcot, 1976; Bauder, 2001; Bauder and Brock, 2001; Buckman and Brady, 1967; Chen and Banin, 1975; Frenkel *et al.*, 1978; Hanson *et al.*, 1999). Soil dispersion results in reduced soil permeability because as the soil disperses it causes to block the soil pores. When soil is repeatedly wetted and dried and clay dispersion occurs, it then reforms and solidifies into cement-like soil with little or no structure. The three main problems caused by sodium-induced dispersion are reduced infiltration, reduced hydraulic conductivity, and surface crusting.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the determination of the soil’s physico-chemical properties, soil samples were taken according to standard methods through stratified random sampling. The area was divided into two strata’s on the basis of soil’s type i.e. saline and non-saline. Each stratum was then divided into clearly homogenized 5 different sites and sub sampled to collect one composite sample for analysis. Sub samples were collected heterogeneously from 10 different places within 2 hectares of the same site and then mixed well for one sample. Same procedure was repeated again for each soil sample collection at the depth of

20 cm from both the strata and was then analyzed for different physical and chemical parameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Salinity and soil pH of the study area

pH is the activity of hydrogen ion and it is the expression of soil acidity or alkalinity. The results of pH for Saline and Non-Saline Soil are presented in table. It can be seen from these results that the pH values of Non-saline soil ranged from 7.85 (Site 1) to 8.3 (Site 3) with an average of 8.05. These results shows that there was less variation in all the sites of non saline soil as represented in Figure below and all the sites were having alkaline pH. These results are in accordance to the Rashid and Memom (2005) who stated that due to the richness in basic ions (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺) of arid and semi arid areas of Pakistan have alkaline pH. Samples of Non-saline soil were within acceptable limits because as studied by Tisdale *et al.*, (1985) pH in the range of 7.76 to 8.46 does not strongly affect the availability of macronutrients (N, P and K). According to (Greenet *et al.*, 2006) soils having range of pH between 5.6-6 are moderately acidic, soils with a pH range between 6.1-6.5 are slightly acidic, soils with a pH range between 6.6-7.4 are neutral or nearly neutral, soils with a pH range of 7.4-7.8 are slightly alkaline, soils with a pH range between 7.4-8.4 are moderately alkaline and soils with a pH above 8.5 are strongly alkaline. Based on this classification, the soil samples collected from Non-saline area were moderately alkaline and the soil samples of saline area were strongly alkaline. The high soil pH values causes to imbalance the solubility of various ions and influences the biological activities (Song and Ishiquro, 1990).

Average pH for Non-Saline and Saline soil						
Soil type	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5	Mean
Non-Saline		7.85	8.2	8.3	7.9	8.0
						8.05
Saline		10.0	8.57	9.02	10.65	11.45
						9.92

Salinity and Electrical conductivity (EC)

Total soluble salts are expressed in terms of electrical conductivity (dsm⁻¹). EC for saline and non-saline sites are represented in Figure which shows that saline soil have higher values as compared to the non saline soil sites. EC values of saline sites ranged from 5.2 (Site4) to 23.9 (Site1) with an average value of 12.8dsm⁻¹. According to Bohn *et al.* (2005) these values are in saline limits and as U.S. Department of Agriculture define soil with an EC greater than 4.0 dS/m as saline. These high EC of study area is due to the calcareous parent material, topographical position i.e. low lying area and high water table i.e. due to water logging which causes accumulation of salts in soil. The increase in electrical conductivity (EC) for saline soil is due to the presence of soluble salts such as chlorides and sulphates of sodium calcium and magnesium in higher concentration which directly affect the growth of plants (Elgharably, 2008).

Salinity and soil Texture of the study area

Soil texture is the relative proportion of the various size soils separates i.e. clay, silt and sand in a soil material. The results of average value for soil texture

of the study area are given in table. The clay content of the sample ranged from 3.8% to 11.25% with an average value of 7.51% for all the soil samples. The silt content of the samples ranged from 35% to 40.5% with an average value of 37.99% and the sand content of soil varied from 50.62 to 58.1 with an average value of 54.51%. Therefore soil textures for all non saline sites were fall in the class of sandy loam. While the results obtained on the texture of the saline samples as presented in table 4.3, revealed that the soil texture of saline sites was silt loam for all the samples. The clay content of the samples ranged from 12.7% to 24.4% with an average value of 18.74% for all the soil samples. The silt content of soil varied from 53.5% to 61.1% with a mean value of 60.62% and the sand content ranged from 14.5% to 33.7% with an average value of 19.66%.

This difference in the soil texture of the study area may due to the topography and variation in the parent material which is mainly alluvial deposit. These results are in accordance to the study of Asim, (1999) and Kamran, (2008) reported worked on the same area of Swabi scarp.

Site	%clay		%silt		%sand		Textural class	
	Saline	Non-saline	Saline	Non-saline	Saline	Non-saline	Saline	Non-saline
1	22.0	10	57.6	37.5	19.9	52.5	Silt-loam	Sandy loam
2	21.0	5.6	53.5	40.5	25.5	53.9	Silt-loam	Sandy loam

3	12.7	53.6	60.2	38.13	33.7	50.62	Silt- bam	Sandy bam
4	13.1	3.8	61.1	38.8	25.8	57.45	Silt- bam	Sandy bam
5	24.4	6.9	61.1	35	14.5	58.1	Silt- bam	Sandy bam
Average	18.74	57.36	60.62	23.88	19.66	54.51	Silt- bam	Sandy bam

Table: Average textural class for Saline and Non-saline soil.

Salinity and sodicity has no impact on soil texture as studied by Rashid and Memon, (2005) the texture of soil is permanent property which can't be changed due cultivation and management practices.

Bulk density (apparent density) of soil is the mass of a unit volume of dry sample including pore spaces. It was found that the bulk density for saline soil was greater as compared to the non saline soil. Soil bulk density increases with increasing salinity and sodicity. These results also support the study conducted by Shakir *et al.*, (2002) and Waller and wallender (1993) who also founds the same results.

Salinity and soil bulk density

Soil type	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5	Mean
Saline	1.45	1.50	1.55	1.59	1.60	1.54
Non Saline	1.29	1.38	1.44	1.30	1.31	1.34

Table: Average B.d (gm/cm³) for Saline and Non-saline soil.

According to Rashid and Memon, (2005) saline soil has high bulk density as compared to normal soil. Therefore it is cleared from results shown that bulk density increases with increase in salt levels (SAR) due to compaction of soil into aggregates (Shakir *et al.*, 2002). Soil organic matter and management practices decreases soil bulk density (Dorado *et al.*, 2003; Rashid and Memon, 2005.). That's why non saline sites 1 (1.29), 4 (1.30), and 5 (1.31) have less bulk density even their texture is coarse than sites 2 and 3. Also salinity makes the soil vulnerable to erosion because it increases bulk density and easily replicates the soil into particles (Cavigeli and Thein, 2004); Bauderet *al.*, (2003).

Salinity and soil porosity

Porosity of soil is the fraction of the soil volume not occupied by soil particles. Results of porosity are presented in figure and table 4.5. Non-saline values ranges from 45.7 (Site 3) to 51.7 (site 5) with an average value of 48.54 while saline soil values ranges from 39.24 (site 5) to 42.97 (Site 1) with an average value of 40.89. Results show little difference among saline and non-saline sites as shown in Figure because soil porosity is dependent on the texture, structure and organic content of the soil. Salinity and sodicity have great impact on soil porosity because it causes to decrease the pore spaces or fill it with water content (Rashid and Memon 2005). The soil porosity and permeability may be reduced due to the soil high pH and sodicity (Pearson and Bauder, 2003; Rengasamy *et al.*, 2003).

Table 4.5: showing soil porosity for Saline and Non-saline soil.

Average %Porosity for Saline and Non-saline soil							
Soil type	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5	Mean	
Non-saline	50.2	47.9	45.7	47.2	51.7	48.54	
Saline	42.97	41.89	40.75	39.62	39.24	40.89	

Salinity and SAR (Sodium adsorption Ratio)

According to (Rashid and Memon, 2005) SAR is used for the prediction of the exchangeable sodium status of soil. The soil sodicity is directly associated with SAR. The results of Sodium adsorption Ratio for saline and none saline soil samples are given below. The SAR values for Non-saline soil ranged from 0.633 (site 1) to 8.72 (site 3) with an average of 4.6mmol/L. Site 1 (0.633), Site 4 (1.51) and Site 5 (3.83) of the non saline soil shows low SAR value because of the addition of organic materials like chemical fertilizers,

compost in soil samples as they were collected from the field where previous crop was tobacco (Sarwar, 2008; Zaka *et al.*, 2003). Results show clear difference of SAR between saline and Non-saline soil samples. SAR is very low in Non-saline area as compared to saline area and there is no sodicity or salinity problem in the Non-saline area as the average SAR ratio were below (10-13) which meant that Na contents in the soil was low and is usable while saline sites are disturbed due to salinity which results in higher SAR values. According to (Ghadiri *et al.*, 2004). soil erosion can be caused due to high soil sodicity.

Site	Non-saline	Saline
1	0.633	10.68

2	8.123	11.06
3	8.72	12.54
4	1.51	15.03
5	3.83	15.24
Mean	4.6	12.91

Salinity and Soil Extractable Sodium (Na⁺)

All sites of saline soil were rich in Na⁺ concentrations and higher than Non-saline sites. Na⁺ concentration in all the soil samples of saline sites ranged from 139.4 to 193.35mgL⁻¹ with average of 167.16mgL⁻¹ while the values for Non-saline ranges from 7.94(Site1) to 121.12(Site 3) with an average value of 54.994mgL⁻¹. Results show significant difference among the sodium status of saline and Non-saline soil. Sodcity is based on the relative concentration of Na⁺ other cations (i.e. Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺) which are adsorbed to soil particles on the exchange complex (Russell,

1961).According to Richards *et al.*, (1956)exchangeable sodium content is directly increased due to the soluble salts. As the Na⁺ concentration in the soil increases it accumulates on the clay particles and causing sodicity(Rengasamy, 2006).The deleterious effects of sodium on soil structure is the increased dispersion and erosion the soil(Schmittner and Giresse, 1999; Evett and Dutt, 1985) because as Sodium attached to clay surface it restrict air and water transport in soil profile and could promote soil erosion and total loss of soil (Quirk and Schofield, 1955).

Soil type	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5	Mean
Non-saline	7.94	81.6	121.12	19.6	44.71	54.994
Saline	119.64	161.78	139.4	192.64	193.35	161.362

Salinity and extractable Ca²⁺ + Mg²⁺

Concentration of Ca²⁺+Mg²⁺ in soil saturation extracts for Non-saline sites varied from 201.84mgL⁻¹ (Site 2) to 386.98mgL⁻¹ (Site 3) with an average value of 302.68mgL⁻¹.While extractable Ca²⁺+Mg²⁺ concentration for saline sites varied from 113.54mgL⁻¹ (Site 5) to 427.52mgL⁻¹ (Site 2) with an average value of 273.43mgL⁻¹ as shown in table . results show that saline and sodic soil has less Ca²⁺ + Mg²⁺ content than that of Non-saline soil.

Salinity and soil NO₃-N

NO₃-N concentration in Non-saline sites ranged from 38.9mg^l⁻¹ (Site1) to 11.1mg^l⁻¹ (Site3) with the average value of 25.44mg^l⁻¹. While saline sites ranged from 16mg^l⁻¹ (Site2) to 0.92mg^l⁻¹ (Site5) with an average value of 6.02mg^l⁻¹. These results obtained for NO₃-N in Non-saline and Saline soil reveals that the concentration of NO₃-N in soil is strongly affected by salinity and sodicity in soil. Nitrogen is the most growth limiting factor for the crops (Graham and Vance, 2000). It is an essential component of proteins, nucleic acids, hormones and chlorophyll (Kozlowski, 1985; Hopkins, 1999). Nitrogen demand by plants is therefore high compared to other nutrients. Thus as the amount of NO₃-N is lower in saline soils as Kadir and Paulsen, 1982).

Soil type	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5	Mean
Non-saline	38.9	19.2	11.1	32.7	25.3	25.44
Saline	3.45	16	7.6	2.13	0.92	6.02

Table showing Average NO₃-N concentration (mg^l⁻¹) for Saline and Non-saline soil.

Salinity and soil Mehlich-3 plant-available Phosphorous (P)

Phosphorous is the second major nutrient essential for plant growth (Arnon, 1943). The available phosphorus is that portion of phosphorous which is extracted by different chemical extraction and is available for plant uptake (Rashid and Memon, 2005). Study findings shows that the saline soil has average less values of Phosphorous as compared to the non saline soil sites of the study area. Following table shows the values for saline and Non-saline sites of the study area. The lowest value in Non-saline sites is 7.14 (Site 3) and the highest value is 8.5 (Site 1) with an average value of 7.92mg^l⁻¹ while saline sites ranges from 3.18(Site 5) to 7.09(Site 3) with an average value of 5.15mg^l⁻¹ as given

below. These results are in accordance to the study of Khattak (1991a) who noticed that AB-DTPA-soluble P ranged from 0.62 to 21.84. Khattak, (1991b) also found that the concentration of P tends to decrease when saline water is used for irrigation. The comparison of saline and non-saline soil results of the study area shows that Salinity, sodicity and alkalinity effects the concentration of P in soil. This statement is also supported by other studies like Curtin *et al.* (1993);Awad *et al.* (1990); Prafitt, (1978);[Naidu and Rengasamy, \(1993\)](#); Saini, (1970); Sharpley *et al.* (1992); Rimmer *et al.* (1992); Aslam *et al.* (1996); Balba, (1980) and Mashali *et al.*, (1988).

Soil type	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5	Mean
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Non-Saline	8.5	7.53	7.14	8.3	8.14	7.92
Saline	5.42	5.06	7.09	5.02	3.18	5.15

Table: showing Average P concentration (mg^l⁻¹) for Saline and Non-saline soil.

Salinity and soil Extractable K⁺

Study results showed that saline soil have less values of as compared to the non saline soil. The highest value for K in Non-saline soil of the study area is 83mg^l⁻¹ (Site 2) and lowest value is 62.6mg^l⁻¹ (Site 2) with the average value of 74.4mg^l⁻¹ as given in table. These results of the study area are in reference to the study conducted by (Ahmad *et al.*, 1986)who also obtained results within these limits. The value for saline sites of the study area varies between 61.2mg^l⁻¹ (Site 2) and 102.4mg^l⁻¹ (Site 3) while the average value is 81.1mg^l⁻¹ as shown in figure and table 4.11. According to clay %age (Ranja, 1988)study also supports these results. The comparison of saline and non-saline soil results of the study area and the given evidences shows that Salinity has great impact on the concentration of K⁺ in soil and tends to increase the concentration of salt K⁺ in soil solution.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It was found that salinity has a great impact on chemical as well as physical properties of soil. Macronutrients like N⁺ and P and micronutrients like Ca⁺⁺ and Mg⁺⁺ are mostly affected as their amount was very low in saline lands compared to non-saline area while salts like Na⁺ and K⁺ was found greater in amount in saline area as compared to non-saline lands which leads to higher SAR values in saline sites. Soil analysis also showed that pH (alkalinity) and EC (salinity) values were high in saline sites compared to non-saline area. Therefore the soil of saline sites falls in saline and saline-sodic category while Non-saline sites were in normal limits. Also bulk density increased due to salinity and sodicity problem in the study area which leads to lower the pore spaces of soil while texture has no exception. Salinity is the major agricultural problem which is adversely affecting the irrigated land and thus directly effects the crops production. Continuous efforts are

needed for combating and eradication of the salinity problems. For successful eradication of salinity and sodicity problems suggested management practices include using ridges/mounds, application of lime (gypsum or oyster shells), organic manures and residues, planting of salt-tolerant crops, agro forestry, leaching and drainage. Other controlling measures include Proper maintenance of the drainage system, leveling, deep ploughing and growing salt tolerant crops like rice and sugarcane, halophytes plants like eucalyptus and grasses like kallar and *Diplachne fusca*. Incorporation of animal manure, household composted materials and growing of green manure crops. Further using gypsum for reclamations its efficiency can be increased by using in the following order. sulphur + manure > gypsum + manure > sulphur > gypsum > press mud + manure > manure > press mud > simple leaching.

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